

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Khisa

FIRST NAME: Abel

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

Key concepts

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. British versus American English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 24-33)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34-39)
5. Style Guides (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-42)
6. Common Latin Abbreviations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 58-62)

KEY TAKEWAYS FROM PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

Cleenewerck & Gulma provide a course pack as a guideline for students as part of ACA-401D. This paper provides an analysis of the key learnings from period one regarding the course pack. The paper identified six concepts for discussions that are useful in delivering quality academic essays using the Turabian Referencing Style. Specifically, the paper highlights takeaway points on essay writing, punctuation, the choice between British and American English, plagiarism, style guides, and common Latin abbreviations.

2) CONCEPTS DISCUSSIONS

a) Essay Writing

The course pack indicates that there are many types of essays and that it would only focus on one type- academic essays. The course pack recommends 1) starting early to enable ample time for reading and studying the literature; 2) defining the main question

and analysing the task to provide answers to the question; and 3) drafting an initial plan containing initial thoughts and ideas – the result of which would determine the type of information to use in answering the question. The course pack also discourages procrastination (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7).

With regards to handing in the essay, the pack instructs students to ensure they know when, to whom, and where to submit the assignments to avoid late submission penalties. I found some of the instructions on essay submission applicable to students physically present in the university. For instance, printing out and stapling the assignment may not be applicable to the online learning scenario.

Finally, the course pack identified eight rules of thumb, including identifying a thesis of the essay and stating it at or near the beginning of the paper, staying focused on the key aspects of the discussion, and not plagiarising. The pack also mentions writing clearly through short sentences of less than five lines, using active voice, and supporting assertions as part of the rules of the thumb. The pack also provides additional requirements for handing in physical copies of assignments. I found it quite confusing when the course pack indicated that the writing ought to have double spacing when the templates provided, such as the one used in this paper, were single-spaced (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7).

b) Punctuations

The course pack provides several directions on various punctuation marks to be used. These guidelines are very much consistent with the grammatical requirements of the English language in general. The course pack also discusses examples, bullet points, different types of brackets, colons and semi-colons, and dashes and hyphens.

i) *Apostrophes*

The pack highlights the use of apostrophes for indicating possession, such as in Abel's to indicate something that belongs to Abel. For names with 'S' as a last letter, there is no need to specify another 'S' after the apostrophe when referring to possession. Apostrophes are not to be used to indicate plurals, especially of abbreviations. For instance, it is wrong to write the plural of MP as MP's. Apostrophes could also indicate missed letters when shortening words that are negated. When so doing, the apostrophe needs to be inserted not in the space between the words but rather ought to act as a placeholder for the words omitted, such as *don't* instead of do not (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 17).

ii) *Hyphens*

Of particular interest is the section that discusses when not to use hyphens. Specifically, the course pack discourages the use of hyphens when creating new compound nouns. Instead, the pack promotes the use of the words involved separately if the subject in question is not a well-known concept or if a known concept combines the two words into one. Examples highlighted as wrong usage of hyphens include e-mail, highly respected, or top-drawer (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 21).

c) British versus American English

The course pack indicates that both American and British English are variants of World English and, as such, have more similarities than differences, particularly within academic and scientific spheres. The variation in vocabulary is also highlighted in the sense of differences in spelling as well as differences in pronunciation for words with similar meanings. For instance, colour and centre are normally spelt color and center, respectively in American English. Americans also prefer the use of four-letter words for obscenities and implied obscenities such as damn compared to bloody in British English. Additionally, the pack identifies the differences in punctuation, such as the use of inverted commas in British English versus quotation marks in American English for verbatim mentions (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 32). I found this section quite enlightening, particularly the cultural differentiation, such as the use of Uncle Sam versus John Bull for euphemistic ambiguities, as well as the full stop that follows the abbreviation Mr in American English as opposed to British English.

d) Plagiarism

In this section, the pack provided the definition of plagiarism as the use of sources without crediting the author of the information. The pack identifies three core reasons why giving credit is beneficial in that it ensures fairness to the author, is an academic offense, and is wrong and unethical. Both in-text citations and a list of works cited are required when attributing credit to authors of sources used with quotations and paraphrases identified as requiring in-text citation. The pack also identifies that it is acceptable not to cite references when the content is common knowledge. Additionally, when some piece of information is repeated in several of the resources that one has, then it can be assumed as common knowledge.

e) Style Guides

The pack also outlined style guides, why they are necessary, and what would normally be contained in them. The pack indicates that style guides are important as they help in keeping the writing consistent, particularly if there are multiple authors for specific documents or write-ups. Additionally, the pack elaborated that different companies, businesses or publications have different writing style guides, leading to there being no single authoritative source on styles. Style guides, as outlined in the pack, cover areas such as but not limited to spelling and grammar, length of sentences as well as trademark or branding considerations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41-43).

I found this section the most challenging to understand. It was not clear to me how broad the scope of the style guides should be nor was it clear how strict Euclid assesses adherence to each style.

f) Common Latin Abbreviations

The course pack also provides a glossary of a range of Latin abbreviations and expressions separately in tabular form and arranged in alphabetical order. I must admit that while I am familiar with some of the abbreviations, most of the expressions were quite new to me. For instance, I was delighted to learn new terminologies such as *viva (voce)*, which means oral examination, and *infra* and *supra*, which means below and above, respectively. Equally, I got to expand my understanding of certain words, such as *caveat* being a word of Latin origin or that *bona fide* does not merely mean genuine or real but could also imply good faith (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 59-65).

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the pack provided a direction on both general and specific concepts that are critical to proper writing. I found the variety of essays discussed in the essay writing sections, the use of symbology discussed under punctuations, the illustration of British and American English, the various notes on recognizing sources to avoid plagiarism as well as the enlisting of common Latin abbreviations invaluable. Additionally, the sample paper provided in the course pack enhanced the understanding of the concepts discussed therein. I believe that moving forward, I would need to keep referring to this course pack in order to stay focussed on EUCLID's requirements as well as to improve my writing skills and English ability.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D. Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.